

Pre-strain effects on CYTOP fibre Bragg grating temperature sensors

A. Pospori*^a, A. Ioannou^a, K. Kalli^a

^aPhotonics and Optical Sensors Research Laboratory, Cyprus University of Technology,
Saripolou 33, 3036, Limassol, Cyprus

ABSTRACT

Cyclic transparent optical polymer (CYTOP) based fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors are of high interest recently due to their lower optical loss compared with the sensors fabricated in other polymeric materials, such as poly(methyl methacrylate). Numerous scientific reports have shown that polymer based FBGs are usually preferred over their silica counterparts due to their enhanced sensitivity to stress and pressure, and their affinity to humidity. Temperature monitoring with polymer FBGs is also extensively demonstrated, but with inconsistent results and non-linear responses, since most of the polymer optical fibres have a negative thermo-optic coefficient and positive thermal expansion coefficient that work to cancel out each other to some extent, resulting in mixed temperature sensitivities. In this work, an optical fibre with a CYTOP core and a Xylex cladding is used to investigate fibre pre-strain effects on the temperature sensitivity of FBG sensors. The sensors were placed in an environmental chamber with controlled temperature and relative humidity, and their response to temperature was evaluated under various fibre pre-strain values. Without any applied fibre strain, the thermal expansion coefficient slightly prevails over the thermo-optic effect, as a result the Bragg wavelength shifts in longer wavelengths. Under sufficient fibre strain, the thermal expansion coefficient is eliminated, and the temperature sensitivity is greatly enhanced, shifting the Bragg wavelength to shorter wavelengths. This paper demonstrates the possibility to have an array of Bragg grating sensors, some being temperature insensitive and some highly temperature sensitive along the same fibre.

Keywords: Polymer optical fibre, Bragg gratings, temperature sensing

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer optical fibre Bragg grating (POFBG) sensors have a growing interest recently because of their enhanced performance in certain applications compared to the silica-based sensors^{1,2}. The polymeric nature of sensors offers higher flexibility in bending and enhancement in fracture toughness³. Therefore, POFBG sensors can be easily installed or embedded in other structures to monitor mechanical properties (displacement, crack formation, internal stress, deformation), chemical quantities (humidity, pH), and temperature⁴. Temperature measurement experiments with POFBGs are extensively demonstrated, but with inconsistent results and non-linear responses in some cases, since the polymer optical fibre (POF) sensors have a negative thermo-optic coefficient and positive thermal expansion coefficient that work to cancel out each other to some extent, resulting in different temperature sensitivities. The Bragg wavelength shift ($\Delta\lambda_B$) due to temperature change (ΔT) can be expressed as:

$$\Delta\lambda_B = \lambda_{B0} \left(\alpha + \frac{\zeta}{n_{eff}} \right) \Delta T \quad (1)$$

where λ_{B0} is the initial spectral position of Bragg grating, α is the thermal expansion coefficient, ζ is the thermo-optic coefficient and n_{eff} is the effective refractive index of the fibre core. Reports demonstrated that the thermal expansion coefficient can be eliminated under sufficient fibre pre-strain, changing the temperature sensitivity of POFBG sensors⁵. In the case of poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA), the thermo-optic coefficient is larger than thermal expansion coefficient, therefore, removing the thermal expansion coefficient on PMMA POFBGs, enhances the temperature sensitivity of sensors⁴. In addition, the Bragg wavelength will always shift in shorter wavelengths as the temperature increases, with or without any applied pre-strain.

*andreas.pospori@cut.ac.cy; orcid.org/0000-0003-4866-1361

In this work, the temperature response of POFBG sensors fabricated in an optical fibre with a cyclic transparent optical polymer (CYTOP) core and a Xylex cladding is investigated. Perfluorinated optical fibres, such as the CYTOP, were developed to tackle the high optical loss in the near infra-red wavelength region shown by PMMA fibres, with the aim to expand the application of POFBG sensors in large civil structures requiring span of several meters, even kilometers^{6,7}. In the case of CYTOP POFBG, the thermo-optic coefficient ($-5.0 \times 10^{-5}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) is smaller in value than thermal expansion coefficient ($7.4 \times 10^{-5}/^{\circ}\text{C}$), therefore, the Bragg wavelength can shift to longer wavelengths with increasing temperature if there is no elimination of thermal expansion⁸. In this paper, different temperature sensitivities are demonstrated, positive and negative as temperature increases, depending on the amount of the applied fibre pre-strain, for which a grating array is readily demonstrated; this contrasts with complex inscription methods demonstrated in PMMA fibres⁹.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Fabrication of sensors

The FBG sensors were fabricated in a custom-made POF (Chromis Fiberoptics - GigaPOF Custom Fibre 250/20) with CYTOP graded-index core (diameter of $20 \pm 4 \mu\text{m}$) and a Xylex cladding (diameter of $250 \pm 5 \mu\text{m}$) using a femtosecond laser system (High Q laser femtoREGEN) with operating wavelength 517 nm, pulse duration 220 fs, repetition rate 2 kHz and pulse energy 20 nJ. Using the plane-by-plane method¹⁰, the fibre was placed on a high-precision air-bearing translation stage (Aerotech), the laser beam was focused into the fibre core (through fibre cladding) using a long working distance objective lens (Mitutoyo – magnification 50x and NA 0.42) and each Bragg plane (width of $5 \mu\text{m}$) was inscribed transversely across the fibre length and centred in the core. In total, 850 Bragg planes have been inscribed to form each POFBG. First, a single POFBG was fabricated to evaluate the temperature sensitivity of the same sensor under different pre-strain conditions. The reflection spectrum of the single POFBG with 4th order resonance at 1549.66 nm is shown in the Figure 1(a). To demonstrate the concept of having sensors with different temperature sensitivities along the same fibre, an array of 4 POFBG sensors was developed along the same piece of POF with physical distance 10 cm between each Bragg grating. The 4th order gratings were centred at 1526.62 nm, 1550.14 nm, 1564.79 nm, and 1576.53 nm, as depicted in Figure 1(b). After the inscription, each POF was connectorised with silica optical fibre using the butt-coupling method and UV adhesive, for interrogation purposes.

Figure 1: Reflection spectrum of (a) single POFBG and (b) array of 4 POFBG sensors

2.2 Strain and temperature characterisation of sensors

A high-precision linear translation stage was used to strain the fibre and measure the strain sensitivity of POFBG sensors. Then, while the fibre was still strained, it was adhered on a 75 mm glass slide (Thermo Scientific – SuperFrost Ultra Plus), using a UV curable adhesive that has low shrinkage and high resiliency (Norland Optical Adhesive 61 –

MIL-A-3920). It is noted that the POFBGs were adhered to the edge of glass slides (size of adhesive was approximately 5 mm in diameter) and that the contribution of thermal expansion of both adhesive ($2.5 \times 10^{-4}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) and glass slide ($8.36 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) can affect the sensitivity of sensor at the temperature range used in the experiments. In addition, the thermal expansion of Xylex cladding ($6.5 \times 10^{-5}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) also contributes to the overall linear expansion of fibre. Depending on which material the POFBG is adhered to, a calibration of the sensing system as a whole is required before the final application, due to the different material thermal expansion properties. For the characterisation of the temperature sensitivity, the sensors were placed in a climate chamber (Mettler HCP 108), with controlled temperature and relative humidity. The relative humidity was kept constant at $40 \pm 1\%$ and the temperature was changed in steps. The temperature was kept constant for more than 2 hours in each step to ensure constant environmental conditions and minimal readout errors. The Bragg wavelength position was monitored in reflection using a commercial interrogation system (Micron Optics HYPERION si155) by tracking the peak position every minute (Micron Optics ENLIGHT software).

First, the POFBG depicted in Figure 1(a) was used to monitor the temperature without pre-strain and with pre-strain values of 0.04% and 0.5%. Then, the array of sensors depicted in Figure 1(b) was used to demonstrate the possibility to have an array of POFBGs, with different temperature sensitivities along the same fibre. The characteristics of each POFBG is shown in the Table 1.

Table 1: Array of POFBG sensors.

	Bragg wavelength (nm)	Pre-strain (%)
POFBG 1	1526.62	0.50
POFBG 2	1550.14	0.10
POFBG 3	1564.79	0.04
POFBG 4	1576.53	0.00

3. RESULTS

The strain sensitivity of POFBG sensors is $1.27 \pm 0.01 \text{ pm}/\mu\epsilon$, as evaluated from the strain response shown in Figure 2; it is noted the linearity and lack of hysteresis. The single POFBG used to monitor the temperature without pre-strain and with pre-strain values of 0.04% and 0.5% is shown in Figure 3. Without any pre-strain, the POFBG having a sensitivity of $18 \pm 1 \text{ pm}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ shifts to longer wavelengths as the temperature increases. With a pre-strain value of 0.04%, results show a temperature insensitivity ($-5 \pm 4 \text{ pm}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) for temperature range between 30°C and 60°C . Applying pre-strain of 0.5%, the Bragg wavelength shifts to shorter wavelengths with an enhanced temperature sensitivity of $-70 \pm 1 \text{ pm}/^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 2: Strain response of POFBG sensor

Figure 4 demonstrates the possibility to have an array of POFBGs along the same fibre with different temperature sensitivities. The array of 4 POFBGs with different pre-strain values (see Table 1) was placed in the climate chamber along with the silica Bragg grating sensor for reference purposes, and their temperature response was monitored. The silica grating and POFBG 4 (without pre-strain) show positive temperature sensitivity. Introducing a fibre pre-strain in POFBGs 1-3, the temperature sensitivity switches to negative values. It is noted that under sufficient pre-strain (e.g. 0.5% in POFBG 1), the temperature response is linear. Introducing less pre-strain, the thermal expansion of materials contributes to a higher degree as the temperature increases, as a result there is a point where the Bragg wavelength starts to shift from shorter to longer wavelengths. This characteristic is shown in Figure 5, which depicts the Bragg wavelength shift as the temperature increases and decreases with time. The temperature sensitivity of POFBG 3 (green colour) switches from negative to positive above 40 °C due to the small amount of the applied pre-strain.

Figure 3: Temperature response of POFBG under different pre-strain values

Figure 4: Temperature response of POFBG array and silica grating sensors under different pre-strain values

Figure 5: Bragg wavelength shift of sensors as temperature changes with time

4. CONCLUSION

In this work, an optical fibre with a CYTOP core and a Xylex cladding is used to investigate fibre pre-strain effects on the temperature sensitivity of FBG sensors. The sensors were placed in a climate chamber with controlled temperature and relative humidity, and their response to temperature was evaluated for different fibre pre-strain values. Without any applied fibre pre-strain, the thermal expansion coefficient slightly prevails over the thermo-optic effect, as a result the Bragg wavelength shifts in longer wavelengths. Under sufficient fibre strain, the thermal expansion coefficient is eliminated, and the temperature sensitivity is greatly enhanced, shifting the Bragg wavelength to shorter wavelengths. This paper demonstrates the possibility to have an array of POFBG sensors with different temperature sensitivities along the same fibre, positive and negative, depending on the amount of the applied fibre strain during their installation process.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Min, R., Ortega, B., Marques, C, "Latest Achievements in Polymer Optical Fiber Gratings: Fabrication and Applications," *Photonics* 6(2), 36 (2019).
- [2] Webb, D. J., "Fibre Bragg grating sensors in polymer optical fibres," *Meas. Sci. Technol.* 26(9), 092004 (2015).

- [3] Large, M. C. J., Moran, J. H., and Ye, L., "The role of viscoelastic properties in strain testing using microstructured polymer optical fibres (mPOF)," *Meas. Sci. Technol.* 20(3), 034014 (2009).
- [4] Broadway, C., Min, R., Leal-Junior, A., Marques, C., and Caucheteur, C., "Toward Commercial Polymer Fiber Bragg Grating Sensors: Review and Applications," *J. Lightwave Technol.* 37, 2605-2615 (2019).
- [5] Zhang, W., Webb, D. J., and Peng, G. D., "Enhancing the sensitivity of poly(methyl methacrylate) based optical fiber Bragg grating temperature sensors," *Opt. Lett.* 40(17), 4046-4049 (2015).
- [6] Theodosiou, A. and Kalli, K., "Recent trends and advances of fibre Bragg grating sensors in CYTOP polymer optical fibres," *Opt. Fiber Technol.* 54, 102079 (2020).
- [7] Lacraz, A., Theodosiou, A., and Kalli, K., "Femtosecond laser inscribed Bragg grating arrays in long lengths of polymer optical fibres; a route to practical sensing with POF," *Elec. Lett.* 52(19), 1626-1627 (2016).
- [8] Lacraz, A., Polis, M., Theodosiou, A., Koutsides, C. and Kalli, K., "Femtosecond laser inscribed Bragg gratings in low loss CYTOP polymer optical fiber," *IEEE Photonics Technol. Lett.* 27(7), 693-696 (2015).
- [9] Johnson, I., Webb, D. J., Kalli, K., Large, M. C. J., and Argyros, A., "Multiplexed FBG sensor recorded in multimode microstructured polymer optical fibre," *SPIE Proceedings Vol. 7714 Photonic Crystal Fibers IV*, 77140D (2010).
- [10] Theodosiou, A., Lacraz, A., Stassis, A., Koutsides, C., Komodromos, M. and Kalli, K., "Plane-by-plane femtosecond laser inscription method for single-peak Bragg gratings in multimode CYTOP polymer optical fiber," *J. Light. Technol.* 35(24), 5404-5410 (2017).